

UNLOCKING THE ANTIMICROBIAL POTENTIAL OF THE FRESHWATER CRAB (*BARYTELPHUSA CUNICULARIS*)

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Article Received on 15 Nov. 2025,
Article Revised on 05 Dec. 2025,
Article Published on 16 Dec. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17950486>

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How to cite this Article: *Manish Mahajan (2025). Unlocking The Antimicrobial Potential Of The Freshwater Crab (*Barytelphusa Cunicularis*). World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 14(24), 756-765.

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the antibacterial and anti-fungal activities of crab tissue extract. The antibacterial activity of ethanol extracts of crab (*Barytelphusa cunicularis*) were tested against two gram positive and two gram negative bacteria by disc diffusion method. It was revealed that all four bacteria were inhibited by these crab extract. Minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) of the extracts were determined by broth micro-dilution method. Anti-fungal screening was done for ethanol extract of this crab tissue by disc diffusion method with four organism (*A. Niger*, *M. Furfur*, *A. Flavus*, *P. Chrysosporium*). *A. Flavus* and *P. Chrysosporium* were showed resistance by this crab extracts while *A. Niger*, and *M. Furfur* where not show the zone of inhibition. This study has shown that crab tissue extract could provide potent antibacterial and anti-fungal compounds and may possible preventive agents against therapeutic disease.

KEYWORDS: *Barytelphusa cunicularis*, antibacterial, anti-fungal, *A. Niger*, *M. Furfur*, *A. Flavus*, *P. Chrysosporium*.

INTRODUCTION

The freshwater crab (*Barytelphusa cunicularis*) is an important source of food commonly sold in many areas due to the nutritional rich and superb taste in soup making. Importantly, the freshwater crab has potential as an antimicrobial agent.^[1] The crab tissue and soup are consumed as traditional treatment and folk medicine for the purpose of jaundice.^[5]

Comparatively the marine crabs, active against pathogens, are interfering with the immune system, including both hormonal and cellular defence system.^[2] On literature survey of *Barytelphusa Cunicularis*, most of the research on biodiversity and biochemistry, but no specific research on microbial activity on clinical pathogens. Biological activity leads to the development of novel drugs on specific action. In this research different microbial species were studied with crab tissue extract (ethanol extract). The study showed microbial activity from the freshwater crab tissue extracted in ethanol was prepared for the antimicrobial efficiency.

The study has been covering the native effects of the microbial action that might to be cause illness and sometimes death of the patient, set-off protection nearly present as in antibiotics.^[3] Due to infectious diseases half of death are caused in tropical countries. According to WHO surveys around the world 1800 deaths are caused by infectious diseases, half of the children between 1-5 years ages.^[4] To minimise the potential of pathogens with necessary antibiotics develop the novel drug.^[5] The antimicrobial drugs are utilized against therapeutic diseases with reducing its side effects by adjusted conditions and pattern with pathogens.^[6] So important is the strategy of the pharmaceutical field to derive novel compounds from the traditional sources and least traditional sources, they explore drug development. It is a challenge to freshwater biota to source for pharmaceuticals as a parallel natural product.^[7]

Decapod crustaceans participate as natural products for drug development from the last few decades, the pathogenic bacteria present in the cell of invertebrate and they are converting soluble antimicrobial and cytotoxic substances in the haemolymph.^[8] In decapods haemolymph showed certain biological activities, the active components like tectin, clotting factor and antimicrobial peptides were analysed.^[9] Knowledge from the pharmaceutical research many crab species showed reflective activities, they are functioning in the medical field.^[10] The antimicrobial activity of the freshwater crab tissue extracted in ethanol, have been higher efficient compounds for antimicrobial activity.^[11]

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.a. Sample collection

Barytelphusa cunicularis was collected from the northern region of Maharashtra state, India. The adult species was used for extraction, isolation, and further study. The reason for selecting adult species is because these species have more bioactive compounds as compared to juveniles.^[11] After collection, the species were transferred alive in refrigerated containers

of the laboratory. The crab species has proceeded for mercy killing (mechanical treatment) by thermal shock for 15 minutes at -300 0C. Each collected species was dissected individually and the tissue was collected from the abdomen cavity of the crab species. The crude extract was prepared from this tissue and was stored in a dip freezer and used for further study.^[12]

2. b. Preparation of extraction

The tissue material was transferred to the microwave for complete drying to obtain the samples in powder form. Further, the powder was dipped into 500 ml of ethanol for 21 days. The overall process is called a cold maceration process because all bioactive compounds are stable at low temperatures.^[13] This method performed at room temperature and the material dipped in an airtight container. Occasionally sample was stirred for high speed for higher extraction. later the suspension was allowed to settle down. This leads to the diffusion of bioactive compounds from the tissue cell until the equilibrium.^[14] After 21 days the extract was filtered. It was further separated from the bulk material. After that fresh ethanol were added to the bulk immediately for high extraction.^[15] The procedure was repeated many times to ensure the maximum extraction yield. All extract was concentrated with rotator evaporators to remove the excess amount of ethanol. Although this method is timeconsuming however it gives higher yields of bioactive compounds. it is less expensive and can be adaptable at any place. This method is best for thermally unstable compounds. The best thing is that It reduces environmental pollution.^[16]

3. c Bacterial culture

Four bacterial and four fungus strain were selected for this study, namely bacteria are *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus vulgaris* while fungus is *Aspergillus niger*, *Candida albicans*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Phanerochaete chrysosporium* total eight pathogens utilized were obtained from National Collection of Industrial Microorganisms, National Chemical Laboratory (NCL), Pune, 411008, India.

3. d Culture method

Agar diffusion assay also known as disc diffusion method; the 6 mm disc was used for this study. The susceptible test method was preferred in which dilution and disc diffusion method for bacterial while yeast and filamentous method for fungal studies.^[17,15]

Microorganism	Strain Name	Strain reference
Gram positive bacteria	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	NCIM 2079
	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	NCIM 2063
Gram negative bacteria	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	NCIM 2109
	<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	NCIM 2172
Fungi	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	NCIM 545
	<i>Malassezia Furfur</i>	NCIM 3471
	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	NCIM 650
	<i>Phanerochaete chrysosporium</i>	NCIM-1106
NCIM: National Collection of Industrial Microorganisms, National Chemical Laboratory (NCL), Pune 411008 [India]		

2. e Concentration of compounds

Stock solution (1000 microgram per ml) of each compound was prepared in DMSO solvent. Assay carried out by taking concentration 100 microgram per disc. Hi-media antibiotic disc: Chloramphenicol (10 microgram/disc) moistened with water are used as standard.

2. f Media used

Microbiological media used for bacteria and fungi Hi-media agars were utilized at specific conditions.

Microbiological Media	Composition (gL ⁻¹)
Nutrient agar (Hi-media) for bacteria	Sodium chloride- 5.0, Beef extract- 10.0 peptone- 10.0 (P ^H - 7.2)
Potato dextrose agar for fungi (all ingredients of Hi media)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Potato infusion- 200 ● Dextrose- 20 ● Agar- 15 ● Final P^H (at 25⁰ C)- 5.6 ± 0.2

2. g Disc diffusion method for antibacterial activity

Agar diffusion assay (disc diffusion assay) was developed in 1940 (19), this is a regular method in microbiological laboratories for testing microorganisms so above-mentioned pathogens testing by this method. The antibacterial activity was assessed by disc diffusion method, the 6 mm size disc was used for this evaluation.^[15] The nutrient agar plate was incubated 24 hours, after that plate was cleaned with sterile cotton. The disc was struck on a nutrient agar plate aseptically. The stock solution has been concentrated 1000 mg ml⁻¹ of each was prepared in DMSO solvent. Assay carried out by taking concentration 100 mg per disc. The Hi-media antibiotic disc chloramphenicol (10 mg per disc) moistened with water was used as standard. The plate was kept for incubation at 37⁰C for 24 hours. The results have been obtained on careful analysis and examination samples only and in the condition

received, the obtained results were measured in the inhibition zone for each disc which was interpreted in millimetre (mm).

2. h Disc diffusion method for antifungal activity

Antifungal activity was examined by disc diffusion method, 6 mm size disc was used for this evaluation.^[19] The potato dextrose agar plate was used for this analysis, a 6 mm disc was struck on an agar plate. The stock solution was utilized for disc concentration already discussed in disc diffusion method for bacteria. The plate was incubated at 37⁰C for 24 hours, the results were obtained by measuring the diameter of the disc inhibition zone.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Antibacterial activity

Freshwater crab tissue extract was prepared in ethanol for antibacterial activity against the four bacterial strains, the crude extract activity against all four bacteria. The *S. aureus* and *B. subtilis* are gram positive bacteria while *E. coli* and *P. vulgaris* are gram negative bacteria. The *S. aureus* and *E. coli* showed highest inhibition zone it means the freshwater crab tissue showed strong activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* but *B. subtilis* and *P. vulgaris* showed moderate inhibition zone it means that crab tissue have been moderate activity against said bacteria (**Table 3.1**).The crude freshwater crab tissue extract showed highest inhibition zone 15.31 mm and 11.99 mm against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* respectively while moderate inhibition zone against *B. subtilis* and *P. vulgaris* (**Fig. 3.1**).

Table 3.1 Antibacterial activity of the tissue extract form *Barytelphusa Cunicularis*.

Sr. No.	Name of the Organism	Chloramphenicol (standard)	Inhibition Zone (mm)
1	<i>E. Coli</i>	25.97	11.99
2	<i>P. Vulgaris</i>	22.36	8.52
3	<i>S. Aureus</i>	31.35	15.31
4	<i>B. Subtilis</i>	22.87	8.97

Fig. 3.1 Antibacterial activity of tissue extract from *Barytelphusa Cunicularis* against human pathogens. T- tissue extract, C- DMSO control, std. – standard (Chloramphenicol).

3.2 Antifungal activity

The crude tissue extract was examined against the four fungus but activity showed against two fungal strains namely *A. Flavus* and *P. Chrysosporium* (Table 3.2)

The extract showed fungal activity against *A. Flavus* and *P. Chrysosporium* of inhibition zone 7.76 mm and 6.43 mm respectively but against *A. niger* and *M. Furfure* not active, no inhibition zones were found around the disc (Fig. 3.2)

Table 3.2: Antibacterial activity of the tissue extract form *Barytelphusa Cunicularis*.

Sr. No.	Name of the Organism	Amphotericin-B (standard)	Inhibition Zone (mm)
1	<i>A. Niger</i>	14.35	-
2	<i>M. Furfur</i>	17.40	-
3	<i>A. Flavus</i>	16.23	7.76
4	<i>P. Chrysosporium</i>	14.17	6.43

Fig. 3.2 Antifungal activity of tissue extract from *Barytelphusa Cunicularis* against human pathogens. T- tissue extract, C- DMSO control, std. – standard (Amphotericin-B).

4. DISCUSSION

Animals are rich sources of bioactive compounds and most of the compounds are derived from marine biota, but structure determination, synthesis and bioactivities are big problems.^[20] Most of the marine animals set toward the drug discovery due to their clinical potential.^[21] This area is maximum focused for research in many disciplines like chemistry, biology, biochemistry and biotechnology. The bioactive compounds shown by many marine crustains for gram positive and gram-negative bacteria so many researchers published the antimicrobial activity.^[22] The peptides are isolated from many crab species and showed antifungal activity against the human pathogens, so many compounds are exploring drug development.^[23,24] In this research the antimicrobial activity of the crude extract from tissue of *Barytelphusa Cunicularis* was studied against human pathogens toward different organisms. In this study bacterial and fungal strain were used, the bacteria differed gram positive and gram-negative bacteria were utilized for this examination purpose, the *E. Coli*

and *P. Vulgaris* are gram negative while *S. Aureus* and *B. Subtilis* are gram positive bacteria, out of these bacterial strains the crude tissue extract showed 1.31 mm inhibition zone against *S. Aureus* while inhibition zone against the *E. Coli* showed 11.99 mm, so crab tissue extract showed strong activity these organisms. The gram-positive bacteria *B. Subtilis* showed 8.97 mm inhibition zone and gram-negative bacteria *P. Vulgaris* showed 8.52 mm inhibition zone toward the extract; it means that the extract showed weak activity towards these organisms.

The tissue extract of *Barytelphusa Cunicularis* was extensively used for virtual study against the fungal strains, there are four pathogens utilized for this study namely *A. Niger*, *M. Furfur*, *A. Flavus* and *P. Chrysosporium*. But in antifungal activity tissue extract showed weak results against these microorganisms, the extract inactive against the *A. Niger* and *M. Furfure*, while active against *A. Flavus* and *P. Chrysosporium*, inhibition zones are 7.76 mm and 4.43 mm respectively.

From the present study, we concluded that freshwater crab tissue showed significant activity against the pathogen, indicating the presence of most bioactive compounds which can be explored for drug development. The selected microorganisms can be focused on the biosynthetic genes and volatile compounds confirmed their potential to utilize an able source of antimicrobial drug, further study yet requires finishing the development of natural potent drugs in pharmaceutical research.^[25, 26]

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